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Azerbaijan's VET Sector Transformation: The Impact of Policy Borrowing from the EU

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Abstract

Context: International organizations have been increasingly influential in shaping vocational education and training (VET) policies in developing countries. However, the factors that drive the adoption of these policies and the effects of global and national elements on the policy change process are not well researched specifically in the case of relations with the EU and its neighbours. This paper examines the case of Azerbaijan, a non-EU member country that underwent VET system reform with EU assistance.

Approach: The study employs a qualitative research approach and draws on the Cultural Political Economy (CPE) concept and the historical institutionalist perspective. The CPE concept helps to understand how global norms and ideas are translated into national policy, while the historical institutionalist perspective allows for an understanding of the historical processes that have shaped VET system reforms in Azerbaijan. The paper aims to identify the factors that motivated the Azerbaijani government to adopt EU-endorsed VET mechanisms and analyze the political, economic, and cultural aspects that influenced this process.

Findings: The paper analyzes how global and national factors shaped the VET policy reform in Azerbaijan. It shows how the Azerbaijani government cooperated with the EU to adopt the EU-inspired VET system as a solution to domestic challenges, with the EU providing support, knowledge, and technical assistance. It also reveals how local experts and technocrats modified the borrowed mechanisms to suit their political and economic interests. The paper emphasizes the role of global ideological stance of IOs and local governance architecture as major determinants of the policy change process.

Conclusion: The paper shows how the EU influenced the VET policy reform in Azerbaijan, a non-EU member country that diverged from the EU's cultural, economic, and political architecture. The paper reveals how the EU problematized VET underdevelopment, proposed a VET development model, and provided funding and technical assistance that led to the adoption of the EU-inspired VET policy model. The research concludes that policy borrowing is possible even when the international organization does not exercise any obligatory pressure on the country or when the borrower country's context differs from the IO's ideological inclination.

Keywords: Europeanisation, vocational education and training, globalisation, policy borrowing, vet policy reform, EU – Azerbaijan cooperation

1 Introduction

The role of vocational education and training (VET) has been shifting in recent decades with the influence of globalisation and social-economic events such as the economic downturn and financial crises. In this regard, the role of international organisations like UNESCO, the European Union (EU), the World Bank, and the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) in shaping VET policies in developing countries have been debated in

the scholarship (Edwards, 2018; Gilbert & Vines, 2006; Mundy, 1998; Mundy & Verger, 2015). Thus, in Europe, in the case of EU members, various directives featuring mechanisms (like metrics and indicators) were adopted at the macro-institutional level, and states were expected to enact policies that would meet certain models and standards in national VET strategies (Lawn & Lingard, 2002; Witt, 2018). However, the situation differs in the case of non-member European neighbourhood nations, particularly when countries that do not aspire to EU membership follow policies and processes devised by the European Union. This research looks at the experience of Azerbaijan, an EU neighbour country that reformed its VET system based on EU-encouraged policy models and procedures. The study's purpose was to identify the primary factors and elements influencing the Azerbaijani government's decisions to accept EU-supported VET mechanisms within the reform initiative. It also seeks to clarify the contextual (political, economic, and cultural) factors that influence national policymakers in their adoption or rejection of those ideas. The main purpose is to better understand the EU-Azerbaijan policy borrowing in the field of VET and try to identify elements that impact decisions on policy borrowing that go beyond past studies on international political and economic aspects (Langbein & Börzel, 2013).

1.1 Problematization of policy borrowing

Literature on the topic indicates that, on the one hand, neo-institutionalist scholars who endorse the World Culture Theory argue that politicians at the national level are subjected to and subsequently borrow policies backed by international players such as the World Bank or the EU in order to be perceived as legitimate (Ramirez et al., 2016). For these scholars, multinational organisations articulate universal norms, values and virtues, and these common values influence the education policy decisions and preferences of decision-makers operating in different countries, leading to convergence of policies. The soft power of culture plays a leading role in policy borrowing for this group of scholarship, and convergence is a natural phenomenon as a result of the similar policies adopted by the nation-states. Nonetheless, any sort of deviation is classified as „loose coupling“ and acknowledged as an exception to the standard rather than indicating the theory's weakness (Steiner-Khamsi, 2021).

Additionally, a string of scholarship focused on the effects of globalisation on education policies indicate that rather than culture, the economic factor is the main element in policy borrowing. Thus, according to the Globally Structured Agenda for Education (GSAE) concept, the international political economy is the driving force of globalization which also affects the social policies in nation-states. These strings of scholarship observe the emerging complexities of the global capitalist economy and try to determine its impact on educational systems, even as it is implemented nationally (Dale, 2000). Supporters of this idea claim that politicians make VET policy decisions based on international economic and political factors such as conditionality, EU membership, accession, etc. (Sung et al., 2000), and that the participation of international stakeholders in national policy processes is critical to fulfilling national-level education institutional reforms (Edwards & Moschetti, 2021).

There is also a string of scholars, without ignoring the influence of globalisation on the national policy arena, who indicate that policy borrowing cannot be reduced to the formal adoption of specific policies and policy instruments in the national context (Verger & Fontdevila, 2023). Thus, there are factors of a different nature (global, local, material, and ideational) that drive national policymakers towards borrowing of policies but similarly, these factors influence the recontextualization of the borrowed mechanism. Thus, accordingly every nation state is unique as a case that needs to be analysed to understand the motivation of policy borrowing.

The objective of this research is to add to the current global discussions by examining how both global and national elements influence policy adoption and their effects on the institutional framework of VET systems in developing nations. Specifically, this study explores how global

development paradigms and ideas have impacted the VET policy reforms undertaken in Azerbaijan from 2013 to 2019, leading to a notable change in policy direction. However, it is important to acknowledge that the factors behind this policy shift have also influenced political, economic, and social events, which have had a profound impact on the decision-making processes of policy actors.

Although several policy studies have examined the topic and analysed efforts to reform VET systems in Eastern Europe, no systematic research has been conducted thus far to explain the historical processes that shaped the institutional configuration of VET system reforms in post-Soviet countries that are not members of the European Union. This study focuses on the entities responsible for driving change, namely stakeholders, institutions, and policymakers involved in policy adoption. It examines their motivations and the contextual factors surrounding their decision-making process. For this purpose, the research primarily seeks and answers the following questions: To what extent has the EU influenced the reform of the VET system in Azerbaijan? and What are the primary elements (motivations/incentives) that influence Azerbaijan's policymakers' decision to embrace EU-encouraged VET policy models in the VET system reform?

2 Methodology

This study examines the VET policy reform in Azerbaijan as a case study, with a focus on identifying the dominant policy paradigm and mechanism resulting from the reform. Furthermore, the study aims to assess the extent of the EU's influence on the policy change. To achieve these objectives, the study adopts the Cultural Political Economy (CPE) concept developed by Jessop (2010) and enhanced by Verger et al. (2016). This conceptual framework facilitates the understanding of the reasons and methods behind policy dissemination, adoption, and change within the national context, considering the content and ideological drivers involved.

Drawing on previous research that employed the Cultural Political Economy matrix (Maurer, 2012; Sung et al., 2000; Valiente et al., 2020; Verger, 2016) to explore policy borrowing and transfer, this study utilizes the historical institutionalist perspective. It specifically focuses on four factors that influence policy change: Global, Domestic, Soft, and Hard elements. The global material factors examine the economic and political influences of the EU, while the global soft factors identify the cultural and ideational influences shaping policy adoption in Azerbaijan. Simultaneously, the contextual analysis investigates the domestic hard elements that encompass the material factors influencing decisions, and the domestic soft elements explore the local culture and political ideology during decision-making processes.

The pivotal moment of policy change in this study is the adoption of the Law on Vocational Education in Azerbaijan in 2019. This change brought about alterations in the practices and institutional arrangements governing the VET sector, as well as the articulation and justification of new policy objectives, modifications to the policy reference frame, and a shift in underlying philosophical or ideational paradigms (Langbein & Börzel, 2013; Sabatier, 1998). Two types of qualitative data collection were employed to conduct research on this specific topic. In the first stage, policy documents, legislative acts, documentation of EU projects in Azerbaijan, and reports from international organisations were collected. Additionally, elite interviews were conducted with policy makers, policy entrepreneurs, international and local field experts, school managers, and representatives of multilateral organisations to understand the policy adoption process and the key factors influencing decision-making.

Methodologically, this study aims to identify several reasons or historical paths that explain why a global script resonates in a particular context and how it is locally adopted and translated (Verger, 2016). The research employs a critical realist philosophy and a qualitative research methodology. The major findings were derived from a primary examination of grey literature, 20 policy documents, and 24 interviews with high-ranking officials involved in the reform of

the VET sector in Azerbaijan. The themes, categories, and groups of questions are determined based on the CPE conceptual matrix and the documents analysis conducted in initial stage of research.

Consequently, this research employs an interpretative or explanatory case study strategy, following the approaches outlined by Merriam and Yin. This strategy involves the deductive development of conceptual categories to examine initial themes identified from document analysis (Merriam, 1998; Yin, 2014). The case study technique is utilized as it allows for a multi-scalar analysis of a complex phenomenon and enables an in-depth assessment of a single, real-life policy from multiple angles to capture its complexity and uniqueness.

The analysis of documents and interview material utilizes thematic analysis, employing a six-step technique developed by Braun and Clarke (2006, 2021). Thematic analysis is chosen for its ability to approach the material in an open-ended manner, enabling the development of the analysis and reaching conclusions based on both empirical evidence and subjective experiences of participants (Hesse-Biber, 2017). Additionally, discourse analysis (Rogers et al., 2016) of primary qualitative data is conducted using the CPE approach, focusing on examining contextual elements framed within the complexity of intersecting multi-level, multi-scalar (local, national, regional, and global) political forces, social structures, cultural traditions, and economic factors (Verger et al., 2018). The coding of interview data is performed using NVivo qualitative data analysis software. The research has obtained approval from the University of Glasgow College of Social Sciences Ethics Committee.

3 Findings

Drawing on Jessop's Cultural Political Economy (CPE) framework, the policy adoption and change process can be comprehended by three evolutionary mechanisms: variation, selection, and retention (2010). Variation entails the emergence of new practices in a contingent manner, selection involves favouring these practices, and retention encompasses their ongoing implementation. By utilizing the variation, selection, and retention framework, it becomes possible to systematically identify the sequence of contingencies, events, and actions involved in adopting new policy models, as well as the specific factors, both semiotic and non-semiotic, that facilitate or impede policy change. Analysing each of these categories individually allows for developing more nuanced explanations regarding adopting educational policies in particular contexts.

1.2 Variation

Data analysis reveals that both global and national factors, incorporating material and ideational elements, significantly influenced the variation phase of policy change in Azerbaijan's Vocational Education and Training (VET) system. Thus, during the initiation phase of VET policy change, the cooperation between the Azerbaijan government and EU institutions exhibited a rationalistic approach. In other words, the government's top echelons perceived the EU experience as a legitimate model capable of addressing domestic challenges such as the skills gap, demographic pressure, and economic diversification. During this phase, the EU provided support by granting access to knowledge sources, offering technical assistance, and undertaking grand projects to support the transition. The EU's previous experience in assisting the transition of Eastern European former socialist republics also signalled to the government's decision-makers that Azerbaijan could restructure its VET system to bridge the skills gap, align it with the labour market, and meet industry demands for skilled workforce. Importantly, in the initiation phase, the EU and other international organizations played a significant role in drawing attention to the issues within the skills development system through reports and white papers that emphasized the urgency of reform.

1.3 Selection

Conversely, during the selection phase of policy change, the decision-makers at the top levels of the government embraced the EU's models for VET system restructuring, incorporating local experts and technocrats. At the operational level, experts identified a discrepancy between the existing VET system model and the EU model, which the top decision-makers perceived as a legitimate replacement. In this context, the EU supported the design of a VET model that emphasized employer integration, viewed as a form of decentralization within the VET system. Additionally, the EU proposed a cost-sharing model for financing skills development. Although local technocrats warned about contextual obstacles such as the centralized governance structure and the unorganized private sector, which could hinder the implementation of the EU model, the promise of cost-sharing proved appealing to the decision-makers and played a key role in selecting this model. While the initial motivation to embrace the EU-recommended VET model for restructuring was primarily pragmatic, the selection phase was influenced by internal politics, institutional configurations, and the EU's limited knowledge of Azerbaijan's internal decision-making processes. Nevertheless, the EU model, with its focus on employer integration and meeting labour market demands, was ultimately adopted.

1.4 Retention

Consequently, the retention of the chosen policy structure involved minimal involvement from the EU and primarily relied on the participation of local authorities. As the policy direction was determined at higher levels of the state apparatus, institutions and actors at the middle level focused on leveraging the situation and adjusting borrowing mechanisms to maximize their political and economic benefits. Consequently, although the main mechanism for involving employers in the VET system was adopted, the enabling factors necessary for the system to function were omitted from the final legal act. Internal conflicts between institutions and actors in the policy process affected the retention of the main elements of the EU model of skills development. However, it is important to note that the opposition did not solely target the EU model of VET development but rather centred around the specific tools and mechanisms used to implement the selected policy.

Overall, the factors influencing the policy change is indicated in Table 1. The findings of this research indicate that the EU played a significant role in both problematization and the selection of appropriate policy solutions in Azerbaijan's VET system. Specifically, the EU advised the government through the European Training Foundation (ETF) on the problematization of the human capital issue and proposed a VET development model that could be identified as a European model of VET development. In addition, the EU funded a technical assistance project to advise and support the development of the Law on Vocational Education.

Table 1

Factors that influenced the policy change in the VET sector of Azerbaijan.

	Variation		Selection		Retention	
	Ideational	Material	Ideational	Material	Ideational	Material
Global	Problematization of human capital issue	Migrant workers	Cost sharing mechanism	World bank reforms	National Qualifications framework	
				Availability of EU best practice		
Local	Negative image of soviet past	Skills shortage	Centralized governance	Role of Ministry of Education	Negative image of Soviet past	Political power of VET Agency
		Youth demographic change	Paradigm shift to human capital		Low expectations from society	

4 Recontextualization

The European model of VET was appealing to local actors because of its promise to integrate employers into the education system. In other words, the European model envisaged a decentralized VET system with a heavy emphasis on work-based learning, the involvement of employers in decision-making related to the content, governance, and funding of the skills development system. Given the limited financial support for the VET system, decision-makers in top layers of government aimed to involve employers in both content development and funding the skills development system. However, the Ministry of Education was not keen to decentralize the governance of the VET system and give more authority to VET schools and employers. This was primarily due to the limited capacity of the unorganized private sector, insufficient capacity of VET institutions, as well as corporate interests of the Ministry itself.

Thus, the European model of VET, which is more enterprise-led or social partnership-driven and decentralized, made it to the policy agenda and the policy document (the Law on Vocational Education). However, its functionality within a centralized governance system based on a government-led skills development tradition was problematic. Mainly because the primary elements that would enable the enterprise-led or social partnership-driven skills development system in Azerbaijan, including stimulating the private sector with certain cooperation mechanisms and giving more autonomy to govern the VET institutions, including involving employers in governance, were omitted from the new policy. In fact, the government was willing to share the cost of the VET system but not willing to change the governance or financing structure of the skills development to enable the new system.

Overall, the Soviet and socialist past of the country, which had deep sociological roots, as well as the capacity of all local decision-makers, affected the policy change process. The aim to modernize the skills development system to make it responsive to the needs of the labour market was hindered by the unstructured labour market players and the government's unwillingness to make changes in the governance system. The findings of this research showed that Azerbaijan borrowed EU practices in the VET was mainly a pragmatic move by the government aimed to tackle domestic challenges. However, in the later stages the local experts identified that the borrowed package is not completely relevant to the political architecture of the country.

Although some interviewees representing the EU institutions indicated that the relationship in the VET sector between Azerbaijan and the EU during the policy change process was not a policy lending and the EU did not put a condition to change the VET system to a certain way, this study finds that „the menu of the solutions” that was offered to change the VET and address the domestic challenges were limited. In fact, Azerbaijan was free to choose its own model of VET. Still, the EU did not offer any model that would be relevant to the phase of the economic and social development of the country.

5 Conclusion

The literature on this topic indicates that the EU's involvement in the post-Soviet space is fairly monotonous in its relationship with the regional nation-states and that the main motivation of the EU concerning the region was security, and its strategy towards the nation-states was to spread democracy accompanied by a liberal market economy in order to achieve its main goal.

As indicated in this study, the vision of the Azerbaijani government towards economic growth was not in line with the EU's concept of modernization. In other words, the government was seeking to keep the centralized system of governance, did not intend to build its economic system on a liberal market economy with delegating most of its functions to the private sector, and would rather build its economic system on a state capitalist model similar to Russia or China, where the main economic activity had been around state-owned enterprises. In addition to this, although the government had been aiming to diversify the economy, its main source of state income derived from the extraction and export of resources. In fact, most of the resource exports were to the European Union, making the EU the largest economic partner of Azerbaijan.

From the picture described above, it is obvious that, at first glance, the EU's and Azerbaijan's visions diverge in almost all spheres of cooperation. Having security as the main priority towards the region, the EU's cooperation with Azerbaijan was heavily dictated by the energy security of its member states. On the other hand, Azerbaijan's main priority was mainly economic in nature, by exporting its natural resources to the EU member states. Interestingly, the aim of the government of Azerbaijan was rather to build bilateral relationships with different members of the union, rather than building binding cooperation with the EU. Needless to say, the government of Azerbaijan cannot afford to ignore the institutional power and capacity of the European Union but shifts its cooperation focus from the union to the member states depending on the political or economic agenda in the EU, Azerbaijan, or any of the member states.

The research findings of this case study support the idea that the policy borrowing is possible even when the international organization does not exercise any obligatory pressure on the country or when the cultural, economic, and political architecture of the borrower country diverge from the IO's ideological inclination. Furthermore, external pressure is not enough to converge in VET policy, and it is interpreted differently by policymakers, and this can lead to different responses in each political and social context and depending on the priorities of local actors (Valiente et al., 2020). This is because the education sector creates its own demand independent from economic reality most of the time triggered by the social demand. In case of the education sector, although in the 21st century many scholars claim that education and economy are connected by tight coupling (Steiner-Khamsi, 2021), the social demand plays a significant role when borrowing and shaping policies. This reality is highly affected by the political architecture, as well as institutional capacity in the country. Hence, even though international actors like the EU play a role of knowledge hub and influence the spread of policy ideas in the form of programs, the translation of these programs in the local context changes elements of this policy. In addition, this research also supported the idea that path dependency makes it exceedingly difficult to effect dramatic change even after the policies were adopted. This may lead to EU instruments such as the European Qualifications Framework and the European

Credit System for Vocational Education and Training being implemented in line with national training systems rather than transforming them. This supports the idea that when the borrowed policy does not match the cultural, political, economic structure of the borrower country, it remains as a symbolic policy and policy convergence is mostly discursive.

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